

21NRM06 EMC-STD

D5: Report recommending an amendment of Annex B and Annex C of the current CISPR 16-1-1 standard detailing results on the calibration of the measuring receiver and the reference pulse generator along with practical recommendations on the calibration of pulse generators and the measurement uncertainty evaluation

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Glossary

CISPR	Comité International Spécial des Perturbations Radioélectriques
CW	Continuous wave
DRTO	Digital real-time oscilloscope
DSO	Digital sampling oscilloscope
EMI	Electromagnetic interference
FFT	Fast Fourier transform
IF	Intermediate frequency
RF	Radio frequency

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1. Introduction

Measuring receivers are used for the measurement of radio disturbance in the frequency range typically 9 kHz to 18 GHz. The specifications of EMI receivers are given in the international standard IEC/CISPR 16-1-1 [1], which is harmonized in the European Union as EN 55016-1-1 [2]. Generally, the term measuring receiver is used for a general instrument fulfilling requirements of [1], such as a selective voltmeter, EMI receiver, spectrum analyzer or FFT-based instruments operating in the time domain. Traditionally, such receivers contain the quasi-peak (QP) detector and are working on the heterodyne principle. Lately, receivers working in the time domain with digital filters emulating the QP detector are used. The main difference between a measuring receiver and a spectrum analyzer is the presence of pre-selection filters (limiting the spectrum of signals entering the receiver, otherwise its input circuits might be overloaded) and a pre-amplifier (increasing the measurement dynamic range). Metrological characterization of EMI receivers is a requirement of the international standard IEC/ISO 17025:2017 [3] for calibration and testing laboratories and the Annex K of the standard [1].

There are many parameters specified for EMI receivers in [1] or [2], respectively. There are general parameters such as the input impedance, filter selectivity, intermediate and image frequency rejection ratio (for heterodyne-based receivers only), and other spurious responses. Parameters related to the QP detector are recommended to be calibrated using pulse generators – sine-wave voltage accuracy, absolute and relative response to pulses. There are two main principles of generating broadband signals for EMI receiver calibration, namely the baseband pulse generators and pulse-modulated RF generators, which will be described in the following text. The terminology used for the calibration of pulse generators is sometimes not unique and confusing, however, all used quantities have dimensional units V/Hz or its mathematical equivalent. The quantity *spectrum amplitude* is widely used which is defined as $S(f) = 2|V(f)|$, where $|V(f)|$ is the Fourier transform of the $v(t)$ signal in the time domain. For rectangular pulses with amplitude A and duration T (pulse repetition frequency $f \ll 1/T$) we can write $S(f) = 2AT$. The spectrum amplitude is a measure of the amplitude spectrum at certain frequency and usually, it is expressed in $\mu\text{V}/\text{MHz}$ or $\text{dB}(\mu\text{V}/\text{MHz})$. For the definition of the spectrum amplitude, see [4]. Another quantity used in standards is the impulse area defined as $A_{imp} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} v(t)dt$. The impulse area is typically expressed in μVs or $\text{dB}(\mu\text{Vs})$.

Annexes B and C of [1] only discuss requirements and calibration methods for the baseband (nanosecond) pulse generators. It will be shown that the description given in [1] is not sufficient to get reliable and repeatable results across various laboratories and recommendations will be given for clarification of the calibration methods description.

2. Pulse generators

According to [1], a pulse generator is an instrument capable of generating time-domain rectangular pulses, or a pulse-modulated RF signal. Rectangular-like generators use steep rising edges and high amplitudes to cover a broad frequency spectrum and they are typically used for lower frequencies (CISPR bands A/B). On the other hand, the energy of pulse-modulated RF signals is mainly concentrated around the carrier frequency and the generators must be tuned to deliver the required pulse amplitude at a particular frequency. Much lower amplitudes of the signal can thus be used (CISPR bands C/D) which decreases the risk of the EMI receiver damage due to high peak voltages, see Tab. 1. Only the resulting spectrum amplitude and its uniformity is important, whereas it can be achieved in various ways. The specifications of pulse generators for the calibration of a measuring receiver are given in [1] as follows:

The response of a measuring receiver to pulses having an impulse area of 0.022 μ Vs, having a uniform spectrum up to at least 1000 MHz, repeated at a frequency of 100 Hz, shall for all frequencies of tuning, be equal to the response to an unmodulated sine-wave signal at the tuned frequency having an r.m.s. value of 1 mV (60 dB(μ V)). The impulse area produced by the generator shall be known with an error not greater than ± 0.5 dB. The pulse repetition frequency shall be known with an error not greater than 1 %.

2.1. Base-band pulse generator

The base-band pulse generators usually comprise an electrostatic or magnetic field energy-storage device and a switch (formerly mechanical mercury relay, nowadays a solid-state semiconductor switch) that discharges a fraction or all of the energy into a load. Very often the storage device is a charged coaxial line, whereas the pulse duration is given by the electrical length of the line and the impulse area is given by the charge voltage. Pulse shapes other than rectangular are usually achieved by TTL pulse shaping. Very fast rising edges are usually achieved using a nonlinear transmission line, step-recovery diode or avalanche transistors. An example of rectangular pulse parameters is given in Tab. 1.

Band	A	B	C	D
Frequency	150 kHz	30 MHz	300 MHz	1 GHz
Rectangular pulse duration for 0.3 dB $S(f)$ decrease at given frequency	960 ns	4.8 ns	0.481 ns	0.144 ns
Open-circuit amplitude for fulfilling the CISPR impulse area	14.06 V	65.8 V	91.5 V	305.6 V

Tab. 1 Example of rectangular pulse parameters.

In the past, there were various nanosecond pulse generators available on the market (e.g. Picosecond Pulse Labs 1000D, Hewlett Packard HP 8082A, EMG Type 11590 (TR-0307)). Nowadays de facto the only supplier of these generators is Schwarzbeck, Germany (e.g. model IGUU 2916). Calibration methods in this report are demonstrated on the calibration of the following base-band pulse generators:

- Schwarzbeck IGUU2916 (base-band pulse generator, CISPR bands A/B/C/D). The generator is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 CISPR pulse generator Schwarzbeck IGUU 2916.

- Schwarzbeck IGU 2912 (base-band pulse generator, CISPR bands C/D). The generator is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 CISPR pulse generator Schwarzbek IGU 2912.

- Picosecond Pulse Labs PSPL1000D (bas-band pulse generator, CISPR bands C/D). The generator is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 CISPR pulse generator PSPL 1000D.

- Schwarzbek IGLK 2914, the generator is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Schwarzbek IGLK 2914 (CISPR bands A/B)

2.2. Pulse-modulated RF generator

The pulse-modulated RF generator uses a harmonic signal with a rectangular-like pulse envelope. The spectrum is similar to a rectangular pulse (upconverted to the carrier frequency f_c), whereas the maximum of the spectrum is at f_c . The spectrum is uniform in a given bandwidth, which implies that pulses with longer duration can be used with lower amplitudes compared to base-band pulse generators (lower risk of measuring receiver damage). The time-domain signal and its spectrum are schematically shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Pulse-modulated RF pulse in the time domain (left) and in the frequency domain (right).

The spectrum amplitude is calculated as follows

$$S(f) = AT \left| \frac{\sin(\pi\Delta f T)}{\pi\Delta f T} - \frac{\sin[\pi(2f_d + \Delta f)T]}{\pi(2f_d + \Delta f)T} \right|, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta f = f - f_c$, A is the peak pulse amplitude and T is the pulse duration. Generally, the spectrum is not perfectly symmetrical around the carrier frequency (see Fig. 5 right), however, in a narrow band around the carrier frequency and for >15 periods of the RF carrier in the pulse, the spectral non-symmetry is negligible. The spectrum amplitude at the carrier frequency is calculable from the RF power and pulse duration. The energy of the pulse is concentrated around the f_c (freq. domain) and thus it is the only usable solution for receivers without preselection. An example of RF pulse parameters is given in Tab. 2.

Band	A	B	C	D
Frequency	150 kHz	30 MHz	300 MHz	1 GHz
RF pulse duration for 0.3 dB $S(f)$ decrease at the boundaries of selectivity bandwidth	1450 μ s	9.5 μ s	2.4 μ s	2.4 μ s
Peak CW voltage (open-circuit) for fulfilling the CISPR impulse area	9.31 mV	33.3 mV	18.3 mV	18.3 mV

Tab. 2 Example of RF pulse parameters.

Calibration methods in this guide are demonstrated on the calibration of following pulse-modulated RF generators:

- RF-source with pulse modulation SMB 100A (CISPR bands A/B/C/D), see Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 RF-source with pulse modulation SMB 100A (CISPR bands A/B/C/D).

- HP 33120A (pulse-modulated RF source, CISPR bands A/B), see Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 RF-Source with pulse modulation Agilent 33120A.

- HP 83630B (pulse-modulated RF source, CISPR bands C/D), see Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 RF source with pulse modulation Hewlett Packard 83630B.

3. Calibration of EMI measuring receivers

The traditional way of checking the compliance of receivers with the pulse response requirements of the standard [1] is by using a calibrated pulse generator [5]. With the growing popularity of TD EMI receivers (often without input preselection filters), it has been debated for a long how to satisfy their conformance with the CISPR 16-1-1 requirements (quasi-peak detector) without the use of pulse generators that may potentially be harmful to the receiver input. To generate spectrum amplitudes specified in [1], narrow pulses with amplitudes in order of tens or hundreds of volts are needed which may destroy the TD EMI receiver's A/D converter. One option is to use an RF sine-wave signal modulated with periodic rectangular pulses (also used to verify the AVG and RMS detectors). The spectrum flatness and response to pulses can also be fulfilled by other waveforms, such as trapezoidal waveform numerically synthesized by an arbitrary waveform generator [6] or a broadband multi-sine signal, however, this approach is only applicable to CISPR bands A/B, because typical arbitrary waveform generators are limited by the output signal amplitude. The CISPR bands C/D would again require amplitudes in order of tens to hundreds of volts (both for the synthesized trapezoidal and multisine waveforms). Using alternative waveforms with possibly lower energy (i.e. lower required spectrum amplitude) is technically sound as there are no natural or artificial disturbance sources with such high energy measured by EMI receivers in typical EMC testing scenarios. To date, using alternative waveforms with lower energy is not covered by CISPR 16-1-1 [1].

According to Annex K of [1], the demonstration of compliance of measuring receivers with the standard can be provided through the manufacturer's calibration process or using procedures and measuring equipment defined in the standard. It is worth mentioning that the current standardized calibration procedure is tailored to the heterodyne receiver architecture, and it does not consider some specific problems of TD EMI receivers. Specific problems of calibration of TD EMI receivers are summarized, e.g., in [7]. Tests which are quick and easy with frequency-swept receivers (filter selectivity, response to pulses) are rather slow and cumbersome with TD receivers. Often access to internal software constants is needed to check the manufacturer's specifications and conformance with CISPR 16-1-1 correctly. Close cooperation with a manufacturer of such a receiver is then required.

Generally, the manufacturers' calibration process is usually more extensive as it validates not only functions related to disturbance measurements but also checks the instrument's general performance. A list of the typical EMI receiver's parameters that are calibrated includes the input impedance; sine-wave voltage level tolerance; overall pass-band selectivity; bandwidth; frequency tuning accuracy; intermediate frequency rejection ratio; image frequency rejection ratio; other spurious responses (e.g., 3rd order intercept point); limitation of intermodulation effects; limitations of receiver noise and internally-generated

spurious signals; limitation of radio-frequency emissions from the measuring receiver and response to pulses of the weighting detectors etc. Due to the various architectures of EMI receivers, there are four core parameters that each EMI receiver should satisfy to be compliant with [1] (black box approach). These parameters are the sine-wave voltage level tolerance, frequency tuning accuracy, response to pulses (absolute and relative) and weighting detectors (selectivity).

Apart from calibration methods recommended by [1], manufacturers usually define their calibration methods based on the knowledge of the receiver's internal architecture. The calibration procedure is usually given in the Service (Maintenance) manual, whereas instrument-specific settings are recommended. Several examples follow:

Error with pulses:

Test setup: Connect pulse generator to RF input of ESN/ESVN.
 Pulse frequency 100 Hz
 Level 80 dB μ V/MHz \pm 0.1 dB ← pulse generation method not specified

Settings on the ESN/ESVN:
 RF ATT 10 dB
 Mode Low Noise
 Detector QP
 OP Range 60 dB
 Meas Time 500 ms

Test: Check the measuring accuracy at 1 MHz and 100 MHz.
 Nominal level at 1 MHz 33 dB μ V \pm 1 dB
 at 100 MHz 50 dB μ V \pm 1 dB

Fig. 9 Manufacturer calibration method, R&S ESVN40 measuring receiver

Test setup:

- Connect TTL output of function generator with pulse modulation input of the signal generator.
- Connect RF output of signal generator to RF input of ESPI

Pulse generator settings:

- Frequency 128 MHz
- Level -10 dBm
- Modulation Pulse

Function generator settings:

- Waveform Pulse Continue
- Pulse width 5 μ s
- Period 40 ms

Fig. 10 Manufacturer calibration method, R&S ESPI measuring receiver.

CISPR bands	A, B, C/D
level at frequency f	
101 kHz	> 114.6 dB μ V / MHz
1.1 MHz	> 80 dB μ V / MHz
101 MHz	> 80 dB μ V / MHz

Fig. 11 Example R&S ESIB receiver, pulse generator requirements; it can be seen that it is important to characterize the pulse generator in the whole bandwidth, as different receivers have different IF frequencies and pulse area requirements

4. Calibration of base-band pulse generators

According to the CISPR 16-1-1 [1] Annex B, the generator should be capable of producing pulses of adequate impulse area with a spectrum up to 1 GHz as uniform as possible and the impulse area shall be known with measurement accuracy ± 0.5 dB and the repetition frequency with 1 % accuracy. The CISPR 16-1-1 Annex C describes an accurate measurement of the output of nanosecond pulse generators, namely

- measurement of impulse area method
- standard transmission line method
- harmonic measurement
- energy method

Each of the methods will be discussed below with a discussion of the usability of commercial calibration laboratories and typically achievable measurement uncertainty.

A pulse generator can be characterized using several methods. In the EN 55016-1-1 (CISPR 16-1-1) there are specified impulse areas of a typical generator for both open-circuit and 50 Ω load, see Tab. 3. The values in this report correspond to the measurement of the spectrum amplitude (calculated from the impulse area) into 50 Ω nominal load.

Band	A	B	C	D
Frequency range	(9 – 150) kHz	(0.15 – 30) MHz	(30 – 300) MHz	(300 – 1000) MHz
Impulse area (open-circuit)	13.5 μ Vs	0.316 μ Vs	0.044 μ Vs	0.044 μ Vs
Impulse area (into 50 Ω load)	6.75 μ Vs	0.158 μ Vs	0.022 μ Vs	0.022 μ Vs
Repetition rate	25 Hz	100 Hz	100 Hz	100 Hz

Tab. 3 Impulse area of a generator for different bands specified in the EN 55016-1-1 standard.

The impulse area A in [μVs] from Tab. 3 can be expressed as the spectrum amplitude $S(f)$ in [$\text{dB}(\mu\text{V}/\text{MHz})$] as follows

$$S(f) = 20 \log(10^6 A \sqrt{2}). \quad (2)$$

The required spectrum amplitude for particular CISPR bands into 50Ω is then $139.6 \text{ dB}(\mu\text{V}/\text{MHz})$ for band A, $107.0 \text{ dB}(\mu\text{V}/\text{MHz})$ for band B and $89.9 \text{ dB}(\mu\text{V}/\text{MHz})$ for band C/D, respectively. It can be seen from Fig. 9 to Fig. 11 that manufacturers of particular EMI receivers may require different spectrum amplitudes to check the receiver specifications. Commercial pulse generators usually contain an output attenuator so that the pulse level can be adjusted (e.g. with a 1 dB step in Schwarzbeck IGUU 2916). Some pulse generators (e.g. the Picosecond Pulse Labs 1000D) do not allow such an adjustment and the change of the spectrum amplitude at a particular frequency can only be done using a calibrated attenuator in the signal path. A calibration laboratory which aims to calibrate EMI receivers from various manufacturers should then calibrate their pulse generator for many different output level settings.

4.1. Fourier transform of time-domain pulse waveform

This method is not discussed in the CISPR 16-1-1 Annex C, however, it is widely used in calibration laboratories and national metrology institutes due to its simplicity and measurement speed. The spectrum amplitude of the signal is determined from samples in the time domain after applying corrections for the signal path and measurement set-up non-idealities and conversion to the frequency domain. As a sampling device, a digital real-time oscilloscope (DRTO) or an equivalent-time sampling oscilloscope (DSO) can be used. This method is mainly used for base-band pulse generators. Corrections for the cable (attenuator) properties and oscilloscope transfer function must be performed. A DRTO triggers directly the measured pulse. The traceability of DRTO is complicated due to the nonlinear behaviour of modern analog-to-digital converters and the transfer function correction. A DSO needs an external trigger signal, which is usually derived from the measured signal itself (approx. 20 ns delay line is used). The measurement is traceable to the electro-optic sampling system. A general diagram of the measurement setup using the DRTO and DSO is shown in Fig. 5. Typically, 20 to 50 acquisitions of each pulse are taken to calculate the type A measurement uncertainty.

Fig. 12 Typical measurement setup with use of a DRTO (left) and DSO (right).

The measurement equation is the following:

$$S(f) = 20 \log \left(\frac{|V(f)| \sqrt{2} \cdot 10^6 \cdot k_{ATT} \cdot k_{osc}}{N_{FFT} \frac{\Delta f}{10^6}} \right) \text{ [dB}\mu\text{V/MHz]}, \quad (3)$$

where $V(f)$ is a Fourier transform of the voltage trace from the oscilloscope in [V], N_{FFT} is the FFT length in samples, Δf is the frequency resolution in [Hz], k_{ATT} is the total attenuation of the signal path, that is, the cables and external attenuators connected between the generator and oscilloscope, (1), k_{osc} is a factor taking into account the oscilloscope frequency response (1). A cable with attenuators on both sides should be used to reduce the pulse amplitude and improve the mismatch uncertainty.

The attenuation of the cable + attenuators and the reflection coefficient is measured using a vector network analyzer and the calculated frequency-dependent spectrum amplitude is then corrected for the measured attenuation at each frequency. The oscilloscope transfer function is taken into account by adding a small contribution to the measurement uncertainty. A full deconvolution of the oscilloscope transfer function in the frequency domain (impulse response in the time domain) from the measured voltage trace is difficult to perform for DRTOs, whereas it is easier for a DSO (traceable characterization of the DSO's impulse response is offered in several national metrology institutes, e.g. PTB Germany).

The following text shows an example of measured and calculated results. The spectrum amplitude was calculated using (3) from oscilloscope voltage samples corrected for the cable and attenuator and oscilloscope transfer function. The following uncertainty contributions apply:

- impedance mismatch correction
- type A uncertainty was calculated from repeated calculations of the spectrum amplitude for all captured time traces

For a correct calculation of the spectrum amplitude, the following aspects should be considered:

- The averaging can be performed either in the time domain (i.e. creating an “average” pulse shape from many readings, see Fig. 13) or in the frequency domain (i.e. calculating the spectrum amplitude for each measured pulse and then averaging the calculated spectrum amplitudes). Note that the pulse in Fig. 13 is only characterized by approx. 30 time samples. Refining the time resolution makes no additional value as the key requirement is to acquire a sufficiently long waveform epoch (for the frequency resolution of 10 kHz, we need to acquire 0.1 ms time epoch which corresponds to 4 million samples at a sampling rate of 40 GSa/s).

Fig. 13 Averaging of pulse in the time domain. Left: detail of the averaged pulse of the Schwarzbeck IGUU 2916 (red), all measured pulses (green) and minimum/maximum width pulse (black); right: detail of the averaged pulse of the Schwarzbeck IGU 2912

- The DC offset of the measured waveform should be removed otherwise it influences the calculated spectrum amplitude at very low frequencies in the kHz range. The waveform should be periodic (i.e. the amplitude of samples in the beginning and at the end of the waveform should be the same) otherwise parasitic spectral components resulting from the FFT appear at frequencies in the kHz range. In Fig. 14 left it can be seen the case if the pulse amplitude does not drop to zero at the end of the acquired pulse (one would have to acquire a very long trace which increases the computation time). A correction which linearly decreases the pulse amplitude can be applied and then the calculated spectrum amplitude is much smoother (Fig. 14 right).

Fig. 14 Numerical aspects of the Fourier transform affecting the spectrum amplitude evaluation

- An oscilloscope with sufficient vertical resolution should be used (at least 8 or more effective bits at the measured frequency is recommended to evaluate the spectrum amplitude with measurement uncertainty lower than 0.5 dB). As shown in Fig. 15, the noise in the waveform may cause a very large error in the calculated spectrum amplitude (DRTO vertical resolution 7 bits, green curve). When using an 11-bit vertical resolution (DRTO in Average mode), the calculated spectrum amplitude is smoother with much smaller type-A measurement uncertainty. In total 20 pulses were taken from which the FFT was performed and the resulting spectrum amplitude is the average from 20 readings. If a DSO is used, the vertical resolution is usually enough (modern DSOs have at least 14 to 16 effective bits resolution), however, DSOs are less frequent in commercial calibration laboratories.

Fig. 15 Spectrum amplitude of the PSPL 1000D generator calculated from samples acquired by the Tektronix DPO7354C oscilloscope (no averaging – green curve; averaging 128 – red curve)

- The oscilloscope should be locked to a laboratory reference frequency (usually 10 MHz) to maintain the precise time base. For very high sampling rates (e.g. 40 GSa/s) the time-unlocked base errors may cause sampling of the waveform in non-equidistant time instants which after applying FFT leads to spurious components in the signal spectrum.

The measured results of the Fourier transform method for the Schwarzbeck IGUU 2916 generator are summarized in Tab. 4 together with the equivalent QP level which is compared to the actual amplitude setting. The equivalent QP level is calculated as

$$S_{QP}(f) = S(f) + 20 \log \left(\frac{RBW}{1 \text{ MHz}} \right) - R_{QP/PK} \quad (4)$$

where RBW is the actual filter resolution bandwidth (200 Hz for band A, 9 kHz for band B and 120 kHz for bands C/D) and $R_{QP/PK}$ is the ratio of the peak/quasi-peak (dB) for the pulse repetition rate specified for each band (see Tab. 7 in [2]).

Band	Frequency	S(f) (dBµV/MHz)	S _{QP} (f) (dBµV)	Uncertainty (dB) (k = 2)
A	9 kHz	139.90	59.82	0.13
	10 kHz	139.83	59.75	0.13
	50 kHz	139.77	59.69	0.12
	100 kHz	139.79	59.71	0.11
	150 kHz	139.79	59.71	0.11
B	150 kHz	107.11	59.59	0.21
	600 kHz	106.90	59.38	0.23
	1 MHz	106.93	59.41	0.20
	10 MHz	106.94	59.42	0.22
	30 MHz	106.75	59.23	0.22
C/D	50 MHz	90.08	59.66	0.16
	120 MHz	90.04	59.62	0.17
	300 MHz	90.14	59.72	0.16
	500 MHz	90.12	59.70	0.18
	1 GHz	89.57	59.15	0.20

Tab. 4 Measured results of the Fourier transform method;
IGUU 2916 Main generator, amplitude setting 60 dBµV.

Quantity	Estimate	Estimate uncertainty	Probability distribution	Divisor	Standard uncertainty	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			$u(x_i)$	c_i	$u(y_i)$
k_{osc}	0 dB	0.060 dB	normal	1	0.050 dB	1	0.060 dB
k_{ATT}	0 dB	0.020 dB	normal	1	0.020 dB	1	0.020 dB
$M_{ATT-osc}$	0 dB	0.008 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.008 dB	1	0.006 dB
$M_{gen-ATT}$	0 dB	0.001 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.001 dB	1	0.001 dB
type A	0 dB	0.038 dB	rectangular	1.73	0.038 dB	1	0.022 dB
total							0.067 dB
expanded uncertainty (k = 2)							0.13 dB

Tab. 5 Example of uncertainty calculation, band A, $f_{rep} = 25$ Hz, frequency 9 kHz. Quantity							
Quantity	Estimate	Estimate uncertainty	Probability distribution	Divisor	Standard uncertainty	Sensitivity coefficient	Uncertainty contribution
X_i	x_i	$u(x_i)$			$u(x_i)$	c_i	$u(y_i)$
k_{osc}	0 dB	0.090 dB	normal	1	0.090 dB	1	0.090 dB
k_{ATT}	0 dB	0.020 dB	normal	1	0.020 dB	1	0.020 dB

$M_{ATT-osc}$	0 dB	0.029 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.029 dB	1	0.020 dB
$M_{gen-ATT}$	0 dB	0.005 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.005 dB	1	0.003 dB
type A	0 dB	0.061 dB	rectangular	1.73	0.061 dB	1	0.036 dB
						total	0.101 dB
						expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)	0.20 dB

Tab. 6 Example of uncertainty calculation, band C/D, $f_{rep} = 100$ Hz, frequency 1 GHz.

The measured spectrum amplitude of the PSPL1000D pulse generator is shown in Fig. 16. Note that this generator has a separate output setting for each CISPR band, thus the spectrum amplitude for the overall frequency span ranging from band A (9 kHz) to band C/D (1 GHz) is not meaningful.

Fig. 16 The measured spectrum amplitude of the Schwarzbek IGUU 2916 generator. Average spectrum amplitude (red) calculated from 50 readings (grey).

The measured spectrum amplitude of the PSPL1000D pulse generator is shown in Fig. 17. It can be seen that the generator is not suitable for CISPR bands A/B, most probably due to

capacitive coupling of the output at low frequencies. The nominal $S(f)$ from the datasheet is 90 dB(μ V/MHz) for band C/D.

Fig. 17 The measured spectrum amplitude of the PSPL 1000D generator, band C/D, $f_{rep} = 100$ Hz. Average spectrum amplitude (red) calculated from 20 readings (grey).

The measured spectrum amplitude of the IGU 2912 pulse generator is shown in Fig. 18. It can be seen that the generator is not suitable for CISPR bands A/B either. The nominal $S(f)$ from the datasheet is 90 dB(μ V/MHz) in the band C/D.

Fig. 18 The measured spectrum amplitude of the Schwarzbeck IGU 2912 generator, band C/D, $f_{rep} = 100$ Hz. Average spectrum amplitude (red) calculated from 20 readings (grey).

When using this method, one should be aware of several aspects affecting the FFT:

- the sampling length is a critical parameter (both DSO and DRTO)
- the trade-off between frequency resolution and generating spurious components
- frequency resolution can be improved by zero-padding the data array
- DC-Offset or reflections in the time domain can have a significant effect on the FFT
- choice of sampling length: as short as possible concerning the required resolution in the frequency domain
- spurious spectral components can occur after performing FFT (periodical)

4.2. Intermediate-frequency measurement method

This method needs an EMI receiver to downconvert the measured signal to an intermediate frequency (IF), whereas the area of the waveform under the envelope is evaluated. This method is referred to as “video pulse technique” (see e.g. MIL-STD-462 [9]), and it is referred to as “video pulse technique”, and “area method” in [1], [2]. The method uses a pulse signal and a reference CW signal (with a known level) connected to a narrow-band filter, whereas the output of the filter (IF) is acquired using an oscilloscope. The spectrum amplitude is then calculated from the response to both input signals at the frequency of the tuned filter (receiver) as follows:

$$S(f) = U_{rms} / IBW, \quad (5)$$

where U_{rms} (V) is the level of CW signal which causes an equal oscilloscope reading as the pulse signal, and IBW (Hz) is the impulse bandwidth of the used filter. The accuracy of the method is dependent on the accurate characterization of the receiver impulse bandwidth IBW. The spectrum amplitude is calculated as the surface under the pulse envelope (i.e. positive amplitudes only). The measurement setup is schematically shown in Fig. 19.

Fig. 19 Measurement setup of the intermediate frequency method.

The practical procedure is the following: in the first step, the pulse signal from the generator is input to the receiver and the response of the receiver’s filter is captured using an oscilloscope (direct connection using a high-grade cable, without attenuators). The peak-to-peak amplitude of the trace is measured as well. In the second step, a CW sine signal is input to the receiver and its amplitude is changed until the oscilloscope peak-to-peak reading is the same as for the pulse signal. The RMS level of this sine signal is measured using a calibrated power meter (or voltmeter at low frequencies). The attenuation of the cable from the generator to the receiver and from the receiver IF output to the oscilloscope is not important, as it cancels due to the ratio measurement. The measurement equation is,

$$S(f) = 20 \log \left(\frac{2V_{pwm,rms} V_{env}}{V_{osc,pp}} k_{peak} k_{osc} k_{IBW} IBW \cdot 10^6 \right) \quad [\text{dB}\mu\text{V}/\text{MHz}], \quad (6)$$

where $V_{pwm,rms}$ is the voltage across a 50 Ω load of the CW sine signal calculated from the RMS power measured by the power meter in [μV]

V_{env} is the amplitude of the IF pulse envelope (see Fig. 20) in [V]

$V_{osc,pp}$ is the peak-to-peak amplitude of the receiver response (IF output) to a CW sine signal measured by the oscilloscope in [V]

IBW is the receiver impulse bandwidth in [Hz]

k_{peak} takes into account the uncertainty of the peak ratio of the response to pulse/CW signal (dimensionless)

k_{osc} takes into account the oscilloscope frequency response (dimensionless)

k_{IBW} takes into account the uncertainty of the determination of the impulse bandwidth (dimensionless).

The receiver impulse bandwidth is calculated as,

$$IBW = \frac{V_{env}}{X \cdot \frac{10}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N v_{env,k}} \quad [\text{Hz}], \quad (7)$$

where V_{env} is the amplitude of the IF pulse envelope (see Fig. 20) in [V]

X is the oscilloscope horizontal resolution in [s/div]

N is the number of samples of the envelope [-]

$v_{env,k}$ represents the k -th sample of the IF pulse envelope in [V]

10 takes into account the number of oscilloscope horizontal screen divisions.

Fig. 20 Response of the receiver to a pulse signal + envelope of the signal (left), unfiltered envelope (right).

The determination of the IF pulse envelope can be done using different methods which results in slightly different calculated receiver impulse bandwidth and consequently spectrum amplitude. Either the envelope can be calculated as a moving average of the voltage IF trace (with e.g. 50 - 200 samples window), or it can be calculated as a magnitude of the Hilbert transform of the IF voltage trace (time domain). It is convenient to filter the envelope trace using a low-pass filter to remove the noise (which is obvious in Fig. 20 right). The area under the envelope is then calculated as a sum of the voltage samples divided by the number of envelope samples. Handling the noise at the beginning and end of the envelope trace also makes some difference in calculated results see Fig. 21.

Fig. 21 Handling the noise at the beginning and the end of the filtered envelope, the calculated IBW is 126.7 kHz and spectrum amplitude is 89.01 dB(μV/MHz) (left) and IBW is 127.3 kHz and spectrum amplitude is 88.96 dB(μV/MHz) (right).

The spectrum amplitude was calculated using (7) from oscilloscope samples of the voltage at the IF output of an EMI receiver. Both the receiver’s response to pulses and to an equivalent sine CW signal were acquired. The oscilloscope traces are well repeatable (small type A uncertainty), however, the determination of the impulse bandwidth from the IF pulse envelope may not be a unique task. The IF pulse envelope was calculated as a magnitude of the Hilbert transform of oscilloscope samples

$$v_{env}[k] = H\{v_{osc}[k]\} = \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{i=k-odd} v_{osc}[i] \frac{1}{k-i} = \frac{2}{\pi} \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} v_{osc}[i] \frac{\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{2}(k-i)\right)}{k-i} = \frac{2}{\pi} v_{osc}[k] * \frac{\sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{2}k\right)}{k}, \quad (8)$$

where v_{env} is the discrete envelope of the oscilloscope samples v_{osc} , symbol $H(\cdot)$ denotes the Hilbert transform and operator $(*)$ stands for convolution in the time domain. The Hilbert transform was implemented in MATLAB using the command `hilbert(x)`. Removing noise at the beginning and the end of the calculated envelope influences the calculated impulse bandwidth and consequently the spectrum amplitude, see Fig. 21. This process is taken into account as a part of the total uncertainty of the spectrum amplitude.

Band	Frequency	S(f) (dBμV/MHz)	S _{QP} (f) (dBμV)	Uncertainty (dB) (k = 2)
A	9 kHz	139.84	59.76	0.21
	10 kHz	139.87	59.79	0.21
	50 kHz	139.83	59.75	0.21
	100 kHz	139.84	59.76	0.21

	150 kHz	140.25	60.17	0.21
B	150 kHz	107.40	59.88	0.12
	600 kHz	107.20	59.68	0.12
	1 MHz	107.06	59.55	0.12
	10 MHz	107.05	59.53	0.12
	30 MHz	106.54	59.03	0.12
C/D	50 MHz	89.62	59.20	0.14
	120 MHz	89.20	58.79	0.14
	300 MHz	88.96	58.54	0.14
	500 MHz	88.57	58.15	0.14
	1 GHz	88.61	58.19	0.15

Tab. 7 Example of measured results, IGUU 2916 Main generator, amplitude setting 60 dB μ V.

Quantity X_i	Estimate x_i	Estimate uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Probability distribution	Divisor	Standard uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
k_{osc}	0 dB	0.050 dB	normal	1	0.050 dB	1	0.050 dB
k_{peak}	0 dB	0.050 dB	normal	1	0.050 dB	1	0.050 dB
k_{IBW}	0 dB	0.080 dB	normal	1	0.080 dB	1	0.080 dB
$M_{cable-osc}$	0 dB	0.0043 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.003 dB	1	0.003 dB
$M_{gen-cable}$	0 dB	0.0009 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.001 dB	1	0.001 dB
$M_{rec-cable}$	0 dB	0.0001 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.0001 dB	1	0.0001 dB
type A	0 dB	0.0080 dB	rectangular	1.73	0.005 dB	1	0.005 dB
total							0.107 dB
expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)							0.21 dB

Tab. 8 Example of uncertainty calculation, band A, $f_{rep} = 25$ Hz, frequency 9 kHz.

Quantity X_i	Estimate x_i	Estimate uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Probability distribution	Divisor	Standard uncertainty $u(x_i)$	Sensitivity coefficient c_i	Uncertainty contribution $u(y_i)$
k_{osc}	0 dB	0.050 dB	normal	1	0.050 dB	1	0.050 dB

k_{peak}	0 dB	0.050 dB	normal	1	0.050 dB	1	0.050 dB	
k_{IBW}	0 dB	0.005 dB	normal	1	0.005 dB	1	0.005 dB	
$M_{cable-osc}$	0 dB	0.0043 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.003 dB	1	0.003 dB	
$M_{gen-cable}$	0 dB	0.0083 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.006 dB	1	0.006 dB	
$M_{rec-cable}$	0 dB	0.0007 dB	U-shaped	1.41	0.0005 dB	1	0.000 dB	
type A	0 dB	0.0110 dB	rectangular	1.73	0.006 dB	1	0.006 dB	
							total	0.071 dB
							expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)	0.14 dB

Tab. 9 Example of uncertainty calculation, band C/D, $f_{rep} = 100$ Hz frequency 1 GHz.

4.3. Measurement of pulse amplitude and duration

This method uses an oscilloscope, whereas the pulse is sampled with high time resolution. The method is most suitable for pulse-modulated RF generators (see later). The method, however, is also applicable to base-band pulse generators. The pulse shape should be very close to rectangular, which is not always true, see the measured pulse shapes of different generators in Fig. 22 to Fig. 24. The pulse amplitude and duration is measured using an oscilloscope. The pulse shape in the time domain is generally distorted by the transfer function of the cable + attenuator(s) and the oscilloscope transfer function. To remove this effect correctly, one has to perform a deconvolution of the transfer function in the frequency domain. The pulse shape, however, was acquired using a short oscilloscope epoch (only the pulse visible on the screen), which makes the frequency resolution very coarse and the correction is not easily applicable.

$$S(f) = 20 \log \left(\sqrt{2} A \cdot k_{ATT} \cdot \Delta T \cdot \left| \frac{\sin(\pi f T)}{\pi f T} \right| \cdot 10^6 \right) \quad [\text{dB}\mu\text{V}/\text{MHz}], \quad (11)$$

where A is the sum of voltage samples in the pulse trace in [μV],

ΔT is the time resolution (sampling time) in [s],

T is the total duration of the pulse in [s],

f is the frequency in [Hz],

k_{ATT} is the attenuation of the cable + attenuator between the generator and oscilloscope.

An example of the pulse shape of different base-band pulse generators in different CISPR bands is shown in Fig. 22 to Fig. 24 for changing the pulse repetition rate. It can be seen that for all studied generators the pulse shape is almost identical independent of the pulse repetition rate.

Fig. 22 Pulse shape for bands A/B/C/D of the IGUU2916 Main generator with changing pulse repetition rate, detail of the pulse maximum on the right (amplitude without correction for the cable and attenuators).

Fig. 23 Pulse shape of the PSPL 1000D generator with changing pulse repetition rate, detail of the pulse maximum (bottom left) and the pulse tail end (bottom right); amplitude without correction for the cable and attenuators.

Fig. 24 Pulse shape of the Schwarzbeck IGU 2912 generator with changing pulse repetition rate, detail of the pulse maximum (bottom left) and the pulse tail end (bottom right); amplitude without correction for the cable and attenuators.

It can be seen from Fig. 22 (Schwarzbeck IGUU 2916 generator) that the pulse shape in bands A and B is close to rectangular and the calculation results are comparable to other methods. The pulse shape of generators PSPL 1000D and IGU 2912 in band C/D (see Fig. 23 and Fig. 24), however, is distorted and it contains more noise than in the case of the pulses in bands A and B.

The results shown below are only informative and they do not correspond very well with the results of the Fourier transform method or the IF pulse measurement method. The pulse shape (measured in the time domain) must be corrected for the attenuation of the cable + attenuator(s) between the generator and the oscilloscope and also for the frequency response of the oscilloscope. The pulse shape trace was acquired only for a small number of points, thus there is not enough data for performing the correct deconvolution and the correction was only done approximately. From Fig. 22 also certain overshoots and

undershoots are obvious. The measurement uncertainty mainly comprises the cable + attenuator correction, impedance mismatch and type A uncertainty. It is obvious that this method is better suitable for pulse-modulated RF generators and not the base-band pulse generators.

Calculated results (values in bold red deviate significantly from results of other methods):

Band	Frequency	$S(f)$ (dB μ V/MHz)	$S_{QP}(f)$ (dB μ V)	Uncertainty (dB) ($k = 2$)
A	9 kHz	139.81	59.73	0.22
	10 kHz	139.81	59.73	0.22
	50 kHz	139.68	59.60	0.22
	100 kHz	139.24	59.16	0.22
	150 kHz	138.49	58.41	0.22
B	150 kHz	106.86	59.34	0.22
	600 kHz	106.86	59.34	0.22
	1 MHz	106.85	59.34	0.22
	10 MHz	105.95	58.43	0.22
	30 MHz	96.40	48.89	0.23
C/D	50 MHz	90.94	60.53	0.25
	120 MHz	85.85	55.44	0.25
	300 MHz	78.35	47.94	0.25
	500 MHz	73.91	43.50	0.25
	1 GHz	45.79	15.38	0.26

Tab. 10 Example of measured results, IGUU 2916 Main generator, amplitude setting 60 dB μ V.

The reason for the large deviation of some results from the results of other methods may be the presence of noise and undershoots or overshoots in the pulse trace. It can be

shown that the contribution of these components to the total surface in [V·s] is significant. The signal is noisy and especially in band C/D, the error can be reduced by summing over only those samples, which correspond to the pulse (the choice of samples may be subjective). This is demonstrated in Fig. 25 and Fig. 26. A relatively long time epoch must be acquired to get reasonable frequency resolution and correct the time-domain trace for the cable and attenuator insertion loss. If the pulse area is calculated over all samples (time epoch of 100 thousand samples = 0.1 μs, including the noisy areas 1 and 3 from Fig. 25 with nonzero energy), one gets wrong results. The trace shown in Fig. 25 is an average from 20 measurements. If the area is only calculated over samples corresponding to the main pulse (approx. 4000 samples, see Fig. 26), the results are more convincing, but still not fully comparable to other methods.

Fig. 25 Demonstration of the summing area for the pulse amplitude calculation.

Fig. 26 Detail of the main pulse from Fig. 25.

Similar results have been obtained for generators PSPL 1000D and IGU 2912 (band C/D only). The pulse was sampled with a relatively coarse timing resolution (25 ps). The parts corresponding to the noise were removed from the waveform before the pulse area calculation. Results of the IGU 2912 generator are summarized in Tab. 11. The pulse shape is far from rectangular in the band C/D and this method does not give reliable results.

Band	Frequency	S(f) (dB μ V/MHz) Fourier transform	Uncertainty (dB) ($k = 2$)	S(f) (dB μ V/MHz) from pulse area	Uncertainty (dB) ($k = 2$)
C/D	50 MHz	91.3	0.17	86.2	0.25
	120 MHz	91.4	0.18	81.1	0.25
	300 MHz	91.8	0.20	73.6	0.25
	500 MHz	90.9	0.19	69.2	0.25
	1 GHz	89.7	0.20	41.1	0.26

Tab. 11 Example of measured results, IGU 2912 generator, amplitude setting 60 dB μ V.

Another tested generator was the Schwarzbeck IGLK 2914. The pulse amplitude and duration were measured directly using the oscilloscope's built-in cursor functions. The generator settings and measured results are summarized in Tab. 12.

CISPR Band	Measured amplitude of pulse A (V)	Measured pulse duration t (ns)	Pulse surface A*t (μVs)
A	50.689 ± 3.72 %	267.2 ± 0.03 %	13.544 ± 2.73 %
B	48.344 ± 3.83 %	6.37 ± 1.16 %	0.308 ± 3.00 %
C	144.59 ± 3.37 %	0.362 ± 4.08 %	0.052 ± 4.84 %

Tab. 12 Example of measured results, IGU 2912 generator, amplitude setting 60 dBμV (pulse repetition rate 25 Hz for band A and 100 Hz for bands B, and C).

Fig. 27 The view of pulse shape of the Schwarzbeck IGU 2914 generator during calibration for band A and band B

4.4. Measurement of one spectrum line amplitude

The principle of this method is a comparison of one spectrum line of the pulse signal with a known CW signal spectrum (equal frequency). This method assumes the generator pulse repetition frequency is high enough so that only one spectral line falls within the EMI receiver filter bandwidth, see Fig. 28. The nominal filter bandwidths for the 6 dB amplitude drop are 200 Hz (band A), 9 kHz (band B) and 120 kHz (band C/D), respectively. This method is referred to as “harmonic measurement” in [1], [2].

Fig. 28 Measurement of one spectrum line amplitude.

The spectrum amplitude is then calculated using a simple formula

$$S(f) = \frac{A}{f_{rep}}, \tag{9}$$

where A is the substitution CW signal level for the same reading of the receiver and f_{rep} is the generator pulse repetition frequency. A calibrated measuring receiver is needed in this case. The measurement setup is shown in Fig. 29. The receiver filter should be well-symmetrical.

Fig. 29 Measurement setup for the measurement of one spectrum line amplitude.

The maximum pulse repetition rate of the Schwarzbeck IGUU2916 generator is 200 Hz, thus only band A could be possible to verify. The maximum pulse repetition rate of the Schwarzbeck IGU 2912 generator is 200 Hz, yet this generator is only suitable for band C/D and thus this method cannot be tested. The repetition frequency of PSPL1000D is set externally from an arbitrary waveform generator up to 1 MHz. The pulse shape must not change significantly with the pulse repetition frequency, which is satisfied (see Fig. 23, where the pulse shape is almost independent of the pulse repetition rate).

The peak pulse amplitude in the band C/D (IF bandwidth 120 kHz) was measured using the R&S ESCS30 EMI receiver for two different pulse repetition rates (i.e. 400 kHz and 1 MHz, respectively). The agreement with the Fourier transform of the time-domain pulse waveform is very good. The EMI receiver reading is more stable for the pulse repetition rate of 1 MHz.

Band	Frequency	pulse repetition rate (kHz)	$S(f)$ (dB μ V/MHz) Fourier transform	Uncertainty (dB) ($k = 2$)	$S(f)$ (dB μ V/MHz) one spectrum line	Uncertainty (dB) ($k = 2$)
C/D	50 MHz	400	89.22	0.20	89.63	0.26
	120 MHz		88.78	0.21	88.79	0.26
	300 MHz		87.73	0.26	87.95	0.26
	500 MHz		86.08	0.34	86.95	0.26
	1 GHz		81.41	0.45	81.55	0.26
C/D	50 MHz	1000	89.22	0.20	89.99	0.25
	120 MHz		88.78	0.21	88.40	0.25
	300 MHz		87.73	0.26	87.71	0.25
	500 MHz		86.08	0.34	86.61	0.25
	1 GHz		81.41	0.45	81.24	0.25

Tab. 13 Example of measured results, PSPL 1000D generator

4.5. Measurement of the transmission line parameters

This method is applicable for generators with charged transmission lines (TL) and certain types of switches. The spectrum amplitude at low frequencies is determined as

$$S(f) = 2AT \tag{10}$$

where A is half of the DC voltage charging the TL (generator output impedance = receiver input impedance) and T is 2x the time of the pass of the signal through the TL. A typical generator with a charged transmission line is depicted in Fig. 30. The switch presents undesirable parasitic L, R, C, the switch must resist twice the TL voltage and thus modifications have been introduced (see, e.g., the US Patent 2,791,101 Transmission Line

Pulse Generator). The through-time is not easy to determine (propagation velocity, other parts of the generator are charged together with the TL). An alternative solution is to measure the capacitance C and characteristic impedance Z_0 of the TL and then T can be calculated as

$$T = 2Z_0C . \tag{11}$$

This method is applicable for very high-voltage generators where other methods are not appropriate and was not tested in the framework of the 21NRM06 EMC-STD project.

Fig. 30 Pulse generator based on a charged transmission line

4.6. Energy method

This method compares the power produced by a thermal source (resistor R) with that produced by the pulse generator [8]

$$\bar{P} = \frac{1}{TR} \int_0^T V^2(t) dt = \frac{2f_r}{R} \int_0^\infty |A(f)|^2 df , \tag{12}$$

where T is the pulse repetition period, R is the resistance of the resistor, $|A(f)|$ is the amplitude spectrum of the voltage $V(t)$. For measurements in a narrow bandwidth the $|A(f)|$ can be considered constant

$$\bar{P} = \frac{2f_r |A(f)|^2}{R} , \tag{13}$$

The spectrum amplitude $S(f)$ is then calculated as

$$S(f) = \sqrt{2} |A(f)| = \sqrt{\frac{PR}{f_r}} . \tag{14}$$

The amplitude response and linearity of the power meter must be flat with frequency, otherwise it must be corrected. A thermistor power sensor or a thermocouple with DC substitution is used. This method was not tested in the framework of the 21NRM06 EMC-STD project.

5. Calibration of pulse-modulated RF generators

Only selected methods will be presented here.

5.1. Fourier transform of time-domain pulse waveform

The principle was described in detail in section 4.1 and the same measurement set-up is used. Pulse-modulated RF signal has a much smaller peak amplitude than a signal from the base-band pulse generator because most energy is concentrated around the carrier frequency. It is, however, still recommended to use an attenuator in the signal path as it improves impedance matching. For a base-band pulse generator, the spectral amplitude can be determined for all frequencies within the CISPR band from just one oscilloscope measurement. In the case of the pulse-modulated RF generator, the oscilloscope waveform must be acquired for each frequency separately. Examples of calculated spectrum amplitudes for the HP 33120A and HP 83630B generators are shown in Fig. 31.

Fig. 31 Example of calculated spectrum amplitudes. Generator HP 33120A, band A, pulse repetition rate 25 Hz (left); generator HP 83630B, band C/D, pulse repetition rate 100 Hz (right)

5.2. Intermediate-frequency measurement method

The principle of the method was described in Section 4.2. The pulse-modulated RF signal from the generator is connected to the EMI receiver input and the IF output voltage is

sampled using an oscilloscope and compared with a CW signal level which produces the same reading of the EMI receiver. Three different RF generators have been tested:

- HP 33120A (band A, B up to 5 MHz) + EMI receiver R&S ESCS30 + oscilloscope Tektronix DPO7354C. The generator allows a very precise setting of pulse duration (given the number of periods of the CW signal) and the output does not contain any transitions or other parasitic effects. The typical time domain voltage is shown in Fig. 32, the measured results are summarized in Tab. 14.

Fig. 32 Typical output of the HP 33120 generator pulse-modulated RF signal (frequency 1 MHz, duration 10 periods)

Band	Frequency	$S(f)$ (dB μ V/MHz)	Uncertainty (dB) ($k = 2$)
A	50 kHz	139.62	0.31
	100 kHz	139.66	0.31
	140 kHz	139.64	0.31
B	1 MHz	106.98	0.27
	2 MHz	106.93	0.27
	5 MHz	106.35	0.27

Tab. 14 Example of measured results, HP 33120A generator measured using the intermediate frequency method

- HP 83630B (bands B/C/D above 10 MHz) + EMI receiver R&S ESCS30 + oscilloscope Tektronix DPO7354C. The CW level of the generator slightly changes after switching on the pulse keying. The pulse duration is set directly in seconds. The typical time domain voltage is shown in Fig. 33. As can be seen, the pulse is not ideal, and the theoretical

spectrum amplitude must be corrected for the true pulse duration. The non-ideality of the rectangular shape is part of the measurement uncertainty.

Fig. 33 Typical output of the HP 83630B generator pulse-modulated RF signal (frequency 50 MHz, duration 10 periods)

Band	Frequency (MHz)	S(f) (dB μ V/MHz)	Uncertainty (dB) ($k = 2$)
B	10	107.52	0.28
	20	107.09	0.27
C/D	30	90.13	0.27
	50	90.20	0.27
	100	90.23	0.28
	200	90.29	0.27
	300	90.42	0.28
	500	90.29	0.28
	700	90.18	0.27
	1000	90.18	0.28

Tab. 15 Example of measured results, HP 83630B generator measured using the intermediate frequency method

5.3. Measurement of pulse amplitude and duration

The spectrum amplitude is calculated from the area of the pulse [V·s]. The ideal measurement equation can be written as follows

$$S(f) = U_{rms} \cdot T \cdot k_{cor}, \quad (15)$$

where U_{rms} is the un-modulated CW signal level, T is the modulation pulse duration and k_{cor} is a correction factor taking into account the signal level change after switching ON the pulse. The pulse repetition rate should be stable and the correction factor should not change with CW frequency. The voltage and pulse duration were measured using a DRTO.

The results in table 16 (show in logarithmic units) were obtained using the setup below, where the processing part includes envelope calculation and integration of the oscilloscope signal to get the pulse area.

Fig. 34 Setup used during the measurement of pulse amplitude and duration.

Band	Frequency (MHz)	Amp (mV)	Pulse duration (us)	Nominal S(f) (dBuV/MHz)	Measured S(f) (dBuV/MHz)	Correction (dB)	Unc (k=2) (dBuV/MHz)
A	0.009	4.7	1450	136.67	136.82	-0.15	0.24
	0.01	4.7	1450	136.67	136.8	-0.13	0.24
	0.05	4.7	1450	136.59	136.68	-0.09	0.24
	0.1	4.7	1450	136.59	136.6	-0.01	0.24
	0.15	4.7	1450	136.59	136.63	-0.04	0.24
B	0.15	16.7	9.5	103.98	103.85	0.13	0.24

	0.6	16.7	9.5	103.98	104.62	-0.64	0.24
	1	16.7	9.5	103.98	104.50	-0.52	0.24
	10	16.7	9.5	103.98	104.21	-0.23	0.24
	30	16.7	9.5	103.98	104.02	-0.04	0.24
C	30	9.2	2.4	86.83	86.94	-0.11	0.25
	50	9.2	2.4	86.83	86.87	-0.04	0.25
	120	9.2	2.4	86.83	87.21	-0.38	0.24
	300	9.2	2.4	86.83	87.12	-0.29	0.24
D	500	9.2	2.4	86.83	87.09	-0.26	0.24
	1000	9.2	2.4	86.83	87.58	-0.75	0.25

Tab. 16 Example of measured results, R&S SMB 100A, pulse amplitude and duration measurement

In a similar way as discussed for the base-band pulse generators, this method can suffer from noise inclusion in the pulse area calculation from samples between the pulses. Adjusting the integration time to samples corresponding to the pulses can reduce this effect. An example measurement uncertainty for frequency 500 MHz can be seen in the table below.

No.	Source	Estimate uncertainty [dB]	Distribution	Distribution factor [-]	Uncertainty contribution [dB]
1	Cable Attenuation calibration	0.020	Normal	1.00	0.020
2	Mismatch DUT - RF-cable	0.020	U-shaped	0.71	0.014
3	Mismatch RF-cable - Oscilloscope	0.020	U-shaped	0.71	0.014
4	Oscilloscope Measurement	0.022	Normal	1.00	0.022
5	Type A	0.115	Normal	1.00	0.115
Total (k=1)					0.12
Expanded uncertainty (k=2)					0.24

Tab. 17 Example of uncertainty calculation for pulse amplitude and duration method at 500 MHz

6. Recommendations on the CISPR 16-1-1 revision

- The current CISPR 16-1-1 standard describes the typical internal architecture of an EMI receiver (e.g., chapters 4 to 7). The text, however, is tailored to frequency-swept heterodyne receivers because at the time of the development of the standard, no other receivers were available in the market. Nowadays, also other principles of EMI

receivers are used (FFT-based receivers, time-domain receivers using mixing to zero frequency with very broadband analogue-to-digital converters, oscilloscope-based EMI receivers working in time domain without input hardware preselection filters). More details should be given to these novel architectures as well with respect to specific measurement issues in the time domain.

- In Annex B of the standard, a general method for the accurate determination of the absolute value of the spectrum amplitude is given with further details given in Annex C. Both Annex B and Annex C describe calibration methods for base-band pulse nanosecond pulse generators. Very little attention is given to the calibration of pulse-modulated RF generators, where specific problems may arise (e.g. non-ideal rectangular pulse shape of the modulating waveform, possibly insufficient number of CW periods in the pulse for low frequencies in CISPR bands A, B etc.).
- Annex C only summarizes various methods for the calibration of pulse generators without giving more implementation details or discussing possible numerical problems with calculating the spectrum amplitude and its measurement uncertainty. In particular:
 - C.1.2 Area method – calibration laboratories may interpret the total area under the envelope $A(t, f)$ in a different way. As shown in section 4.2, the method how determining the pulse envelope is not unique (taking the noise areas in the vicinity of the envelope into account or not) and also the method for determining the IF signal envelope and integrating the area should be standardised (Hilbert transform, moving average).
 - C.1.3 Standard transmission line method – pulse generators based on the principle of charged transmission lines are rare on the market nowadays. Instead, semiconductor switches or non-linear transmission lines are used where the application of this method is difficult, if not impossible. This section should be revised to contain more up-to-date information.
 - C.1.4 Harmonic measurement – the term “sufficiently high and stable repetition frequency” should be quantified to get repeatable results in different calibration laboratories. The highest pulse repetition rate required for the quasi-peak detector is 100 Hz and in practice, pulse generators with very high repetition rates (where only one spectrum line falls in the filter bandwidth) are not always available.
 - C.1.5 Energy method – this method seems to originate from the 1960s, yet it is not routinely used in calibration laboratories nowadays. The method should be referenced to give readers more information about the recommended

practical implementation and measurement uncertainty sources it is only claimed that the measurement accuracy is “somewhat less” compared to other methods.

- Although the nanosecond pulse generators exhibit relatively flat and broad spectrum up to 1 GHz (band C/D), using alternative waveforms for EMI receiver conformance testing was studied earlier (see, e.g., [6]). Using alternative test waveforms with lower energy is the only method applicable for receivers without a preselector. Moreover, there are only very few pulse generators fulfilling the CISPR 16-1-1 requirements commercially available on the market nowadays and not all calibration laboratories have them at disposal.
- Annex K.3 to K.5 – the calibration recommendations are tailored to heterodyne-principle measuring receivers. Specific properties of time-domain FFT receivers should be discussed as some of the tests may be time-consuming or performed with a lower accuracy (see, e.g., specific problems when characterizing frequency-swept versus time-domain EMI receivers in [7]).
- Annex K.6 (Determination of compliance of a measuring receiver with applicable specifications) – the international document ILAC-G8:09/2019 should be referenced here to give more comprehensive information about the determination of EMI receiver compliance and the concept of sharing the risk of false pass or fail between the calibration/testing laboratory and the end user of the equipment.

7. Conclusion

In this report, various methods for calibration of pulse generators are discussed and results of measurement of the spectrum amplitude of particular pulse generators are given. Both base-band pulse generators and pulse-modulated RF generators were used for the measurements. Usability of particular calibration methods was discussed with respect to the measurement equipment needed, the complexity and achievable measurement uncertainty. It was shown that the standard CISPR 16-1-1 only contains very brief description of particular calibration methods (Annexes B and C of the standard) and that the description allows ambiguous interpretation and thus different results may be achieved by different calibration laboratories. Several recommendations with respect to possible changes and amendments of future editions of the CISPR 16-1-1 standard were given.

8. References

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